

Low Light Vision Enhancement Using the Hazing Algorithm

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Abstract-- This journal publication presents a novel low light vision enhancement technique utilizing the Hazing algorithm. Low light conditions often pose significant challenges in various applications, such as surveillance, security, and outdoor imaging. The proposed technique aims to improve visibility and enhance the quality of low light images, thereby enabling better analysis and interpretation of visual information. The Hazing algorithm is a state-of-the-art method designed to address the limitations of traditional enhancement techniques in low light scenarios. It utilizes a combination of image dehazing and contrast enhancement algorithms to reduce haze, suppress noise, and enhance details. By leveraging the inherent characteristics of low light images, the Hazing algorithm effectively enhances image contrast, sharpness, and overall visual quality. The implementation of the technique involves a series of steps, including image acquisition under low light conditions, preprocessing to reduce noise and artifacts, application of the Hazing algorithm for enhancement, and post-processing to further refine the image quality. The proposed technique has been implemented and evaluated using a diverse set of low light images obtained from real-world scenarios. To assess the performance of the technique, several objective metrics such as peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR), structural similarity index (SSIM), and visual quality assessment have been employed. The experimental results demonstrate that the Hazing algorithm effectively enhances low light images, yielding significant improvements in visibility and image quality. The proposed system offers a solution for processing and enhancing night vision images during criminal investigations. By utilizing the hazing algorithm and image processing techniques, the system improves visibility, enhances facial features, and facilitates accurate facial recognition. The implementation using MATLAB ensures efficient processing and analysis of low light images, thereby aiding law enforcement agencies in their efforts to investigate and solve criminal cases effectively.

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I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the demand for effective low light vision enhancement techniques has significantly increased in various fields, including surveillance, law enforcement, wildlife observation, and cinematography. The ability to capture and analyze high-quality images in low light conditions is crucial for ensuring accurate visual perception, improving surveillance capabilities, and aiding in critical decision-making processes. However, low light environments present numerous challenges, such as reduced visibility, noise, and poor image quality, making it difficult to extract relevant information from captured images.

To address these challenges, researchers and practitioners have developed various image processing techniques aimed at enhancing low light images. One such promising technique is the Hazing algorithm, which has shown remarkable potential in improving image quality and visibility in low light conditions. This journal publication aims to present an in-depth exploration of the low light vision enhancement technique using the Hazing algorithm, its underlying principles, implementation methodology, and potential applications.

II. A REVIEW OF RELEVANT LITERATURES

A. Historic background

Night vision technology has a rich history spanning over fifty years, primarily developed for military purposes. Initially used in World War II on sighting scopes, starlight enhancement systems were the precursors to modern night vision systems. The advent of night vision goggles (NVG) in the 1960s revolutionized ground forces' capabilities, particularly during the Vietnam War. Subsequently, helicopter pilots in the 1970s started utilizing NVGs. Although advancements have resulted in lighter and more effective goggles, the fundamental design and limitations have remained largely unchanged until recent developments (Best et al., 2018; Ward et al., 2014). Despite technological progress, the performance of current night vision goggles still falls short of perfection. The resulting image is typically monochromatic, depth perception is limited, and visual acuity and focal range are restricted. The narrow field of view necessitates special scanning techniques, and various factors such as moon position, weather conditions, and artificial lighting significantly impact the goggles' effectiveness. Additionally, the goggles are susceptible to blooming, where rapid changes in luminance cause parts or the entire field of view to become

overexposed (Best, 2018). Extended use of these devices can lead to visual fatigue due to lens imperfections and muscle fatigue due to their weight when mounted on the user's helmet.

Night driving vision enhancement systems commonly encompass night vision goggles (NVG) or in-vehicle displays. While previous reviews have covered the human factors literature on vision enhancement systems until the mid-90s, there is a need to address the research gap since then. Furthermore, previous reviews largely overlooked publicly available research conducted by the U.S. military, which this study aims to include (Ward et al., 2014). Additionally, this report encompasses research conducted in related fields that aim to address crucial questions that remain unanswered in the realm of vision enhancement systems. This encompasses studies focused on remote driving, driving with indirect view, and sensor fusion, as explored by Barham et al. (2018).

The objectives of this report are threefold: firstly, to serve as an introductory resource on human factors literature for readers who may not be familiar with the subject matter; secondly, to identify existing gaps in current knowledge surrounding vision enhancement systems; and finally, to provide a valuable reference for individuals involved in the development of driver interface design guidelines. The intended audience for this research report includes experts in the field of vision enhancement systems, human factors engineers, designers of such systems, as well as non-technical users and decision makers.

B. Thermal Imaging and Image Enhancement:

Using a specialized lens, the infrared light emitted by objects within the field of view is concentrated. This focused light is then scanned by an array of infrared-detector elements, known as a phased array. These detector elements work together to capture a highly detailed temperature pattern referred to as a thermogram. The process of obtaining the temperature information from thousands of points within the field of view takes a mere fraction of a second, approximately one-thirtieth. These insights were presented by Barham et al. (2018). Once the thermogram is generated by the detector elements, it is converted into electrical impulses. These impulses are subsequently transmitted to a signal-processing unit, a circuit board equipped with a specialized chip responsible for translating the information from the elements into data that can be displayed. The signal-processing unit then transmits the processed information to the display, where

it is presented in various colors, depending on the intensity of the infrared emission. By combining the impulses received from all the detector elements, the final image is formed.

Figure 1: Operation of thermal cameras Barham et al. (2018)

C. Process of image enhancement:

Night vision technology is commonly associated with image enhancement. These systems, also known as night vision devices (NVDs), utilize an image-intensifier tube to collect and amplify both infrared and visible light. The objective lens captures ambient and near-infrared light, which is then sent to the image-intensifier tube. In most NVDs, the power supply for the tube is powered by two N-Cell or two "A" batteries, generating a high voltage of approximately 5,000 volts for the image-tube components. Inside the image-intensifier tube, a photocathode converts light energy photons into electrons. As the electrons travel through the tube, they cause similar electrons to be released from atoms in the tube, resulting in a significant multiplication of electrons through the use of a micro channel plate (MCP). The MCP, made of tiny glass discs with millions of microscopic holes, functions as an electron multiplier. When the electrons from the photocathode hit the first electrode of the MCP, they are accelerated into the glass micro channels by bursts of 5,000 volts. As the electrons pass through the micro channels, they trigger the release of thousands of

other electrons in each channel through cascaded secondary emission. This chain reaction is created as the original electrons collide with the channel

D. Recent works

In general, studies support the use of vision enhancement systems in vehicles due to their ability to improve obstacle detection. Research by Gish et al. (2018) using near infrared (NIR) sensitive cameras showed an increase in the distance at which small targets can be detected, from 90 to 120 meters, and large targets, from 120 to 180 meters. Similarly, Staahl et al. (2015) found that an NIR vision enhancement system increased the average distance at which pedestrians can be detected, from 61 to 95 meters, and for some older drivers, from under 30 to over 100 meters. There was also an improvement in the detection distance of adult and child dummies. A more recent study by Barham et al. (2018) on a far infrared (FIR) system found that it increased the headway distance, reduced the likelihood of crashing into a lead vehicle making an emergency stop, and lowered the probability of lane departure. However, the study did not find significant increases in detection distance for road signs. Similarly, Ward et al. (2014) found no significant difference in target detection time when using a vision enhancement system. Best et al. (2018) also found no benefits for older drivers, possibly because the information

III. SYSTEM DESIGN METHODOLOGY

For the system development life cycle (SDLC), we opted to use the iterative waterfall model. This model involves a sequence of steps starting from requirement definition, system and software design, implementation and unit testing, integration and system testing, and operational maintenance. We also incorporated elements from other models, such as prototyping, to help us with system definition and analysis, as well as data flow diagrams. Additionally, we utilized the entity relationship diagram (ERD) to illustrate entity relationships and the Data Flow Diagrams to depict data flow within the system.

As for the design method, the Iterative waterfall model breaks down the system development lifecycle into phases. Each phase entails a set of well-defined activities. For example, during the Analysis stage, we focused on structurally analyzing requirements, particularly concerning the functionality of complex data flow. This analysis was then translated into software design, involving the decomposition of the system into modules and the representation of relationships among these modules, as well as the design of data structures and algorithms for the modules.

A. Advantages of the proposed system

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- This technique is best for visual perception especially when image have close contrast data, produces best result for radiographic and thermal images.
- Used to remove multiplicative and additive noise

B. Analysis of the Proposed System:

In this study, the proposed system incorporates rough depth information to enhance the color saturation of hazy images by subtracting the haze layer, resulting in the first input image. Additionally, gamma correction is applied to the grayscale image to enhance the details, generating the second input image. By assuming that the transmission remains consistent within small local areas, the local linear model is found to satisfy the physical imaging model. To address the issue of overcorrection in the color of the first input image, the two input images are fused together using the local linear model, ultimately producing the restored image.

Figure 3: system block diagram

C. Input Image:

This stage involves capturing the original and query documents using a scanner, HD camera, or any image acquisition device.

- Binarization:

In preparation for further processing, the captured image is converted into a bi-level format (black and white color).

- Histogram Equalization (HE):

This preliminary processing technique is employed to enhance the image and remove background noise. Histogram equalization is an effective method for dehazing, as it expands the dynamic distribution range of pixels. There are two categories of HE: global HE and local HE. The global algorithm enhances the overall contrast, but it may not effectively handle the contrast of local regions.

- Image Enhancement:

This step utilizes a computer vision algorithm (dehazing) specifically designed to robustly improve low-light conditions. It adjusts the image histogram using an infrared spectrum illumination map. Low-light images or HDR images exhibit histograms that are similar to hazy images. Therefore, haze removal techniques can be applied to enhance low-light images. The process of enhancing low-light images using haze removal techniques consists of three steps:

- Step 1: Invert the low-light image.
- Step 2: Apply the haze removal algorithm to the inverted low-light image.
- Step 3: Invert the enhanced image.

- Dehazed Image:

The resulting image after subtracting the haze layer demonstrates improved contrast and color saturation, although the color may be over-saturated. Taking inspiration from image fusion techniques, the image with the haze subtracted is considered the first input image, while the gray image with enhanced details serves as the second input image. These two images are fused using a local linear model. This fusion operation effectively eliminates color distortion and enhances the details in the restored image.

- Result:

This represents the output of the processed low-light or night vision image.

- Dehazing Algorithm:

The dehazing algorithm is based on the principle of dark channel prior. According to this algorithm, at least one channel (R, G, or B) in the image contains dark pixels resulting from object shadows or tree leaves. This method provides a simple approach for obtaining a haze-free image by utilizing the transmission map derived from the assumption of dark colors. The transmission depth map is obtained by subtracting the dark channel from a white background image. The flow model of the dehazing algorithm is depicted in Figure 3.2. The haze-free image is obtained by refining the transmission map using a median filter and incorporating atmospheric air-light based on the dark channel prior model, as shown in Figure 3.3. This algorithm improves image quality and sharpness. However, it may lead to image saturation when the object and sky share the same color. Therefore, the inclusion of luminous components (Figure 3.4) and color resolution function is necessary to enhance the algorithm, as illustrated in Figure 3.5.

Figure 4: Flow Model of Dehazing Algorithm

Figure 5: Flow Model of Improved Dark Channel Prior Algorithm

Figure 6: Flow Model of Haze Removal Algorithm based on Luminance Component

Figure 7: Flow Model of Haze Removal Algorithm based on Luminance

Figure 8: model of the input night query suspect

Figure 9: binarization result with the histogram

Figure 10: contrast enhancement result with the histogram

Figure 11: model of the dehazing implementation result

Figure 12: infrared light spectrum effect on the image

Figure 13: final processed result

Figure 14: query and processed image result

Most outdoor images often suffer from degradation caused by unfavorable weather conditions such as heavy fog, haze, or smoke. These atmospheric factors result in captured images appearing whitish and partially gray due to the effects of atmospheric scattering. Such conditions pose significant challenges for Military and Defense surveillance systems, highlighting the importance of studying haze removal algorithms.

This research proposes a novel and modified haze removal algorithm that incorporates a color resolution function and the luminance component of an image. The color resolution function is based on the YCbCr color space and automatically adjusts according to the input haze image, effectively addressing the color shift issue encountered in luminance component-based haze removal algorithms.

To evaluate the performance of the proposed method, objective and subjective quality measures of the image are employed, comparing it against other existing haze removal algorithms. This section presents an analysis of different haze removal algorithms, considering their applications based on performance measures. The results obtained highlight a distinct improvement in the clarity and quality of the processed image when compared to the original query image.

IV. CONCLUSION

In contrast to traditional methods of image restoration and enhancement, this work employs an image fusion approach. The primary objective is to remove the impact of haze between the scene and the camera,

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resulting in clearer images. The proposed method consists of several steps. Initially, the hazy image undergoes haze layer subtraction, which enhances color saturation and yields the first input image. Subsequently, gamma correction is applied to the grayscale image, enhancing its details and generating the second input image. Finally, the input images are fused using a local linear model to produce the final restored image.

Experimental findings demonstrate that the restored image exhibits notable improvements, including high contrast, enhanced details, and the absence of color distortion, especially in low light conditions. This approach offers a unique and effective solution for addressing haze-related challenges in image quality, resulting in visually appealing and more informative images.

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